

“Powering a Greener Benin with Renewable Energy by 2050”

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Energy Modelling Platform Global (EMP-G)

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Context, Challenges, and Research questions

Context and challenges

- ✓ Electricity Access Rate in 2023: 57.0 % (WBG,2023)
- ✓ 63.62% of Benin's GHG emissions outside the LULUCF sector come from the energy sector. (NDC, 2021)

Electricity generation sources, Benin, 2022

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Research questions:

- 1) What is Benin's energy expansion capacity by 2050?
- 2) How could Benin achieve better decarbonization of its electricity generation, cutting associated emissions by half by 2050?
- 3) What is the most cost-effective renewable energy mix that can be implemented to meet energy demand in an environmentally sustainable manner by 2050?

Scenarios

Using the OSeMOSYS Linear Programming Energy System Model the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
BAU	Reference scenario using historical trend	Projection based on historical data and assuming the continuation of current government policies. (Research question 1)
Scenario1	Scenario based on a decrease in CO ₂ emissions from the energy sector by 2050	Cut energy sector emissions, Benin's main source of CO₂, by half by 2050 using a cleaner, more diverse energy mix (Research question 2)
Scenario2	Scenario based on an energy mix (solar, biogas, wind,...) combined with current government policies and Benin's NDC commitments	Increase in renewable energy installed capacity by at least 25% by 2050 . (Research question 3)

RESULTS

Production by Technology By Mode

RESULTS

Accumulated New Capacity

RESULTS

Annualized Investment cost

RESULTS

Annual Technology Emission

RESULTS

Annual Technology Emission

For comparison

CONCLUSION

Both Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 are feasible options. However, Scenario 1 involves a slightly higher cost, 0.06% more than Scenario 2 in terms of Annualized Investment Cost. The two scenarios have similar CO₂ emissions.

If Benin aims to cut its energy-related CO₂ emissions by half by 2050, it can not only meet future energy demand with lower investment requirements, through a more valuable renewable energy mix. However, the country could achieve some additional investment savings (0.06%) if the objective is to Increase in renewable energy installed capacity by at least 25% by 2050.

APPENDICES

Concept Note of TôviLab Power Initiative

This preliminary concept note presents the rationale and objectives of the proposed Living Lab on Energy Modeling and Renewable Energy in Benin. It is included for informational purposes only and reflects the current stage of co-creation with participating stakeholders. Click here for more information: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1WwjHm9jopIEla9p6INpW6EuDbI9tKRhA?usp=drive_link

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Thanks